

INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF CONSUMER GOODS LISTED FIRMS IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of intellectual capital on financial performance of listed firms in the consumer goods industry for the period spanning 2008 through 2019. Specifically, the study attempts to explore the individual effects of intellectual capital sub-components on the performance indicators employed in the study. The data obtained from the audited annual reports of the firm was analyzed using the Driscoll-Kraay panel regression estimator; the study finds that value-added intellectual capital unconditionally improves firms' financial performance in the industry. Subsequently, human and capital employed efficiency exerts a consistent and strong implication on all financial performance measures. Whereas, structural capital efficiency only has significant impact contributions on the returns on equity. The results robustness is confirmed with the use of an alternative estimation technique. Arising from the findings, various policy options are proposed in this study. This study appears to be amongst the few empirical research that considers the consumer goods industry in the intellectual capital-performance nexus. Also, the study had made modest contribution to the literature by employing Driscoll-Kraay panel regression model and in consumer goods industry.

Keyword: Intellectual Capital, Firm Performance, Consumer goods industry, Driscoll-Kraay PSCC

1. Introduction

The debate on the role of intellectual capital in firm financial performance has continued to attract considerable attention in the literature (Bruna et al., 2021; Buallay & Hamdan, 2019; Ginesti, et al., 2018). The increasing attention was due to intellectual capital implications on profitability (Isola, et al., 2019; Li & Zhao, 2018; Ur-Rehman et al., 2021) and firms' wealth creation (Anifowose, et al., 2018; Celenza & Rossi, 2014). Lately, intellectual capital has been perceived as an effective antidote for bankruptcy, thereby improving the organization's efficient utilization of human, organizational and financial capital (Cenciarelli, et al., 2018; Gupta & Raman, 2020). It also enhances business diversification by creating and exchanging intellectual knowledge amongst the employees of an organization (Duho & Onumah, 2019; Stewart, 1997). Further, intellectual capital management in firms exhibits great potentials in enhancing hands-on investment decisions by the shareholders and investors, especially in a knowledge-driven environment (Bayraktaroglu, et al., 2019; Alrashidi & Alarfaj, 2020).

In the knowledge-driven economy, the performances of firms no longer depend on the physical or tangible assets but on their intangible resources such as technological, process, people innovations, as well as efficient relation to external stakeholders (Bruna et al., 2021; Isola, et al., 2020; Li & Zhao, 2018). This proposition is in tandem with the resource dependency theory, which identifies the need to effectively manage and utilize both the internal and external

resources for optimal competitive advantages and improved financial performances (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Wernerfelt, 1984). The theory postulates that the firms' strategic resources should be endogenous, thereby making it rare, imitable and not easily transferable. Given this, these strategic resources are often referred to as hidden resources capable of creating wealth and profitability for the firms (Arranz et al., 2020; Kamukama, 2013; Lu et al., 2021).

Several studies have been conducted to examine the link between Intellectual capital and firm performance (Anifowose et al, 2018; Mohd-Ariff, et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2021; Ofori-Sasu, et al., 2019). However, the findings of the studies are either inconclusive or mixed (Bruna et al., 2021; Buallay& Hamdan, 2019; Ginesti, et al., 2018). Some scholars pointed to intellectual capital as potential resources for firms' growth and survival (Sardo& Serrasqueiro, 2018), while others could not ascertain its impact on firms' financial performances (Ofori-Sasu, et al., 2019; Suraj&Bontis, 2012). Therefore, the debate on the empirical linkage between IC and firm performance is still open for further research.

More importantly, most empirical studies concentrate on the service industries such as banking, insurance, and telecommunications (Mohd-Ariff, et al., 2016; Ofori-Sasu, et al., 2019; Suraj&Bontis, 2012; Smriti & Das, 2018; Xu, et al., 2017). The research concentration is due to the perceived notion that the sectors embrace extensive technological innovations in their intangible business operations (Smriti & Das, 2018). However, in recent time, the non-service industries such as the consumer goods industry are attracting increasing relevance of intellectual capital in their daily operations. The increased attention on intellectual capital management may be attributed to their dynamic market changes, customer demand and preferences.

The consumer goods industry accounts for over two-thirds of the world's market (Bessiere, et al., 2019; Jacobs &Mafini, 2019). It is also an industry that can create up to 80% of the global workforce due to its backward and forward industrial linkages (Jacobs &Mafini, 2019). Thus, if the industry is well-developed and performing, it may enhance the growth of other linkage industries such as the agriculture, advertisement, transport, and the retail industry (Subramanian, et al., 2019). Hence it is an industry that should be reckoned with in line with UN sustainable development goals 8 and 9. The goals stress the need to achieve full employment and economic growth by advancing industrial and innovative sustainable development capabilities.

Furthermore, the consumer goods industry is an industry that is characterized by a high level of competitiveness due to the changing customers' preferences and the dynamically changing economy from a traditional-based to a knowledge-based industry (Subramanian, et al., 2019). Hence, intellectual capital may be an excellent resource for the firms in the industry required to catch- up with the dynamically changing market environment and a hidden source for competitive advantages for the firms. However, the link between intellectual capital and the firms' financial performance in the consumer goods industry is poorly understood in the literature with a particular reference to the firms in Nigeria. Hence, there is a need to empirically verify the impact of intellectual capital on the firms' financial performance in the consumer goods industry.

This study, therefore, contributes to the empirical debate on the link between Intellectual capital and firm performance in the context of the non-service industry with a particular reference to the consumer goods industry in Nigeria. The firms in Nigeria's consumer goods industry offer an excellent research scope because they cater for the second-largest market in Africa. It is also the country with the resource strength in terms of human capital to accommodate the industry's increasing expansion. Also, the study applies a novel regression estimator to account for heteroscedasticity, serial and spatial dependence in the employed dataset. The application of this technique appears novel in the intellectual capital- performance literature.

The preview of the estimated findings is as follows: First, the study establishes a strong and positive impact of intellectual capital on the financial performance of consumer goods industry. Second, the study suggests that human capital efficiency is the main driver of intellectual capital for financial performance in the industry. Third, it points out the efficacy on the board members in driving performance in the industry. The results are robust because the study applies the Driscoll-Kraay panel regression estimator to account for perceived panel-spatial correlations and temporal cross-sectional dependence. Following the introductory section, the next section reviews salient theoretical and empirical literature on intellectual capital and firm performance. Section three deliberates on the methodological approaches, modelling and data while section four presents the results and discussion of findings. The last section concludes with policy inferences and further areas of research inquiry.

2. Review of literature

Extant scholars have adopted different management and economic theories to explain the link between intellectual capital and firm performance. Most prominent among the theories are resource-based, organizational learning, resource dependency theory, and knowledge-based theories. The resource-based theory assumes that firms which are endowed with physical and intangible resources have the capability of having improved financial performance (Wernerfelt, 1984). The theory further assumed that the resources are immobile, rare, imitable, and non-transferable. The distinct characteristics of these resources accrue competitive advantages to the firms and hence improve their financial performances. Mohd-Ariff, et al. (2016) found support for the theory in their positive outcome between intellectual capital and firm performance. However, Tarus & Sitienei (2015) noted that the firm's size matters in analyzing the impact of intellectual capital on firm performances.

The organizational learning theory further stresses the need for continuous learning as essential to accrue the benefits of intellectual capital for firm growth (Njuguna, 2009; Mubarik et al., 2021). He noted that firms could acquire long term growth and sustainability if they could embrace continuous learning. Continuous learning could therefore be attained through investment in research and development. Using the investment in research and development as a proxy for structural capital. Nadeem et al (2018) found support for the theory. Equally, the resource-dependence theory was established in the empirical examinations of intellectual capital's importance to firm performance. The theory popularized by Pfeffer & Salancik (1978)

considered that firms are open to opportunities within their environment. It stresses firms' need to create excellent interrelationships with their external stakeholders to gain their loyalty and confidence. These values serve as relational capital for the organization, and they are capable of building the firm's comparative advantages for increased performance. Cenciarelli, et al. (2018) confirmed that external relationship, efficiently managed by human capital, positively influences intellectual capital's potentials for firm performance. Having discussed the theories and how it influences the link between intellectual capital and firm performance, this study lays its theoretical framework on the resource-based theory. This is because the theory emphasis on the value derived from the stock of internal and external resources for improved capabilities of the firm (Wernerfelt, 1984).

Empirically, the link between intellectual capital and firm performance has been well established in the developed economies (Nadeem, 2018; Sardo & Serrasqueiro, 2018). However, within the developing economies context, empirical outcomes of the relationship are scarce (Anifowose et al, 2018; Isola, et al, 2019). Despite the scantiness, their findings have been inconsistent and inconclusive, leaving the link open for further research. Nonetheless, intellectual capital, being an intangible asset to the firms, has complemented the performance of the tangible and physical assets in delivering value to the shareholders and having a remarkable impact on the firm's profitability. For instance, public firms in the US have effectively employed intellectual capital to reduce bankruptcy incidences, thus increasing profitability (Cenciarelli, et al., 2018). However, the study is limited in exposition because it did not examine the effects of intellectual capital subcomponents on firm performance.

A related study was conducted on the impact of intellectual capital on growth opportunities and listed firms' financial performance in 14 Western European countries. The study adopted the generalized methods of moments to account for the endogenic characteristics of the study's variables. Sardo & Serrasqueiro (2018) found that intellectual capital promotes growth opportunities and the firms' financial performances between 2014 and 2015. This study further confirmed that the subcomponents of intellectual capital have significant impacts on the firms' performance in Western Europe.

Contrary to the strong positive implications of intellectual capital to firm performance in the developed region, the studies in the emerging and developing countries are marred with conflicting outcomes. For instance, Alazzawi, et al. (2018) investigated the implications of intellectual capital efficiency for Indian firms' financial performance. The study, which adopted the hierarchical regression techniques, found a weak correlation between intellectual capital and firm performance. Although, through the moderating effect of technological capital, intellectual capital buffers the firm's performances. All other intellectual capital indicators except human capital exert strong incremental implications on firm performances in India.

More so, Li & Zhao (2018) could not account for a strong influence of intellectual capital for 1850 sampled Chinese firms (in the current period) between the period 2003 and 2015. The study

noted that intellectual capital investments in the previous year produce significant and positive outcomes for firms' performances. The study further noted that human capital efficiency has no significant impact on firm value.

However, in Nigeria, Anifowose, et al. (2018) revealed that intellectual capital efficiency significantly influences the free cash flows and economic value-added of the firms between 2010 and 2014. More so, the findings document that only human capital contributes significantly to free cash flows but not on economic value-added. On the other hand, relational capital reduces free cash flows and economic value-added. Within the same country, Isola, et al. (2019) discovered that intellectual capital has positive but weak implications on the profitability levels of 97 listed firms in Nigeria between the period 1999 and 2004. Upon inquiry on the specific effect of the subcomponents of intellectual on firm performance, the study revealed that only capital employed negatively impacts the profitability of the firms.

Besides, research's conflicting outcomes may be attributed to the lumping of different sectors together in their analysis, given that each sector or industry has its peculiarity. Egungwu&Egungwu (2017) reacted to the concern by examining the effect of intellectual capital on the corporate financial performance of 5 commercial banks in Nigeria. The study employed the ordinary least square regression to analyze the data obtained from the banks' annual reports between the periods 2006 and 2015. The study revealed that intellectual capital has positive contributions to asset quality and profitability but could not influence the banks' quality of loans. However, the outcome of the study could not be generalized because it adopted only a subcomponent of intellectual capital rather than all the components. Also, the study fails to address the endogeneity concerned, which may infer biased or spurious results.

Similarly, Alhassan & Asare (2016) examined the impact of intellectual capital on commercial banks' productivity in Ghana between 2004 to 2011. The study's dataset was analyzed through the use of multiple regression analysis. Overall, the study suggests that intellectual capital increases banks productivity. However, of all the intellectual capital subcomponents, only the impact of structural capital on banks' productivity could not be ascertained. In another study, the effect of intellectual capital was examined on microfinance performance. Hashim, et al. (2018) adopted the convenient sampling method to administer its self-structured questionnaire to the 153 top managers in 22 selected countries across the globe. The study revealed that all the components of intellectual capital significantly impact the financial performance of microfinance institutions.

Still on the financial system, but another sub-sector, Sherif& El-Sayed (2015) evaluated the significance of intellectual capital on Egyptian insurance firms' performance from 2006 to 2011. The study, which adopted the Blundel and Bond estimation techniques, revealed that intellectual capital gains are not accrued to the current year of its investment. This indicated that the previous year's intellectual capital investments positively impacted the current year's financial performances. All other subcomponents of intellectual capital exhibit the same trend except for

human capital efficiency, which produces an inconsistent signal on financial performance in the current and past financial years.

Considering the implications of intellectual capital on other service-oriented industries, Mohd-Ariff, et al. (2016) examined the effect of intellectual capital on the research and development firms' market performance between the period 2006 and 2013. The study employed the multiple regression method to analyze the data obtained from Compustat. The study revealed that only human and technological capital delivers progressively to market performance. Overall, intellectual capital has a weak relationship with the firms' market performance. In a closely related study, Tarus & Sitienei (2015) examined the impact of intellectual capital on the performance of software development firms and the role of firm size. The study opined that intellectual capital and components significantly contribute to firm innovativeness through a moderated regression technique. Furthermore, the study stressed that smaller-sized firms are more innovation conscious than the bigger firms. The impact of intellectual capital was also examined on the telecommunications industry's performances in Nigeria (Suraj&Bontis, 2012). The study found that intellectual capital has a positive but weak relationship with the performance of the Nigerian telecommunication industry.

Although the studies are marred with inconclusive findings, it was observed that most of the studies are skewed towards the service sectors. The reason could be attributed to the fact that the sectors offer intangible services, therefore intellectual capital is only relevant to them. However, the consumer goods industry is an emerging industry that embraces intense competition due to the changing nature of its market and the customers' preferences (Subramanian, et al. 2019). The customers' preferences are increasingly altered based on the availability of a wide variety of opportunities such as the e-commerce. Therefore, it is expedient on the firms to explore opportunities to harness competitive advantages for improved firm performance through sound intellectual capital management. However, to the best of knowledge, there appears to be a dearth of empirical literature on the impact of intellectual capital on the financial performance of consumer goods industry with particular reference to the Nigerian consumer goods industry. The Nigerian consumer goods industry appears to be a potential researchable scope because it currently houses Africa's largest market. The industry also has the potential to attract foreign investment and increase the continent's visibility to the world. Furthermore, the industry is potentially endowed to accommodate a large workforce, thereby reducing unemployment and poverty incidences in the country.

3. Research Methods

3.1 Research methodology and model

The study's research philosophy is based on positivism epistemology. This is because it adopts scientific analysis to examine the link between intellectual capital and firm performance, particularly the consumer goods sector. The research approach is suitable because it allows the researcher to base its research enquiry on the existing knowledge to answer the yet unexplored

research questions (Saunders, et al., 2016). Furthermore, the study utilizes the deductive research approach to create an in-depth understanding and narrow down the general knowledge of the intellectual capital- firm performance nexus to the specific industry such as the consumer goods industry. Given this study's thrust, the relationship of interest is explored by hypothesizing a model to link intellectual capital efficiency, financial performance, and other confounding variables. The baseline model is specified as

$$Performance_{i,t} = \gamma_0 + \delta V_{it} + \beta C_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where V is a vector of intellectual and its sub-components which are human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency. The identifier "C" implies the other set of covariates that can potentially influence firms' financial performance in the Nigerian consumer goods industry. Finally, the identifier “ε” represents the error term that may pose a challenge when the regressors do not exert the same variance and absolute independence with the error term. Hence, the equation may yield a biased inference or result. To address this, the equation is augmented using the Driscoll-Kraay standard errors for coefficients through the panel-spatial correlation consistent (PSCC) estimator (Hoechle, 2006).

Driscoll-Kraay standard errors for coefficients account for possible temporal and cross-sectional dependence by correcting the coefficient estimates' standard errors (Baloch, et al., 2019; Driscoll & Kraay, 1998). Furthermore, the non-parametric estimator is an appropriate technique which effectively handles missing data-points in the case of a balanced or an unbalanced panel dataset (Hoechle, 2006; Sarkodie & Strezov, 2019). By default, the PSCC estimator based its assumption on the fact that the variables exhibit heteroscedastic and contemporaneously correlated across panels with smaller cross-sections (Ikpesu, et al., 2019). Hence, it fits a linear cross-sectional time series model (Reed & Webb, 2010).

3.2 Data

The dataset employed for this analysis is obtained for the annual reports of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria between 2008 and 2019. As at the end of the 2019 financial year, the number of consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) was twenty-one (21). Eighteen were selected because some of the firms were in the process of delisting and those with 5-year data gap.

In a regression analysis, study variables are either explained, explanatory, or controlled variables. For the purpose of this study, the explained variables are the level of financial performance of the firms. The selection of the study's financial performance indicators is based on the established usage of the measurements in extant studies. Stemming on existing studies, financial performance for this study are the returns on assets (Nimtrakoon, 2015; Sardo & Serrasqueiro, 2019) and the returns on equity (Bayraktaroglu, et al. 2019; Ginesti, et al., 2018). Return on assets is defined as the ratio of net income to the closing value of the firm's total assets, while returns on equity is the ratio of net income to the total equity at the close of the financial year.

The independent variables are expressed in line with models adopted in the works of Al-Hassan & Asare (2016), Sardo & Serrasqueiro (2018) and Nadeem, Gan & Nguyen (2018), this study follows the Pulic (2000) definition of intellectual capital to account for the effect of capital employed on firm performance. Based on the above-mentioned research, this study also adopts the Public VAIC model to measure the contributions of intellectual capital to firm performance. Pulic (2000) offers an objective method of evaluating intellectual capital because the study foresees that the effect of intellectual capital may not be fully captured if the impact of financial capital efficiency is not accounted for (Isola, et al., 2019). VAIC is the summation of human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency. Human capital efficiency measures the rate at which human capital contributes to the value-added of the company. Structural capital efficiency, on the other hand, is defined as the contributions of the difference between value-added and human capital to value-added.

The study further incorporates control variables into the model due to their established impact on firm performance. In line with extant studies, the age of the firm, its size and board size are incorporated in the study. The age of the firms is defined as the number of years of listing in the Nigeria stock exchange in line with (Anifowose, et al. 2018). The size of the firm is referred to as the natural logarithm of the firms' total assets, while the size of the board depicts the number of persons in the boardroom of the firms (Cenciarelli, et al., 2018, Duho & Onumah, 2019).

3.3 Preliminary Analysis

Table 1 presents the descriptive analysis and the summary statistics of the dependent variables, independent variables and the control employed in this study. The table reveals that the standard deviation of the two measures of performance (ROA, ROE) are of high series.

Table 1: Descriptive Summary Statistics

	Variable code	obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Table 1: Summary Statistics of the variables</i>	roa	216	0.14	0.36	-1.27	2.82
	roe	216	0.23	0.31	-0.87	1.31
	vaic	216	5.08	4.6	-11.38	32.42
	hce	216	3.88	4.08	-4.79	30.46
	sce	216	0.69	1.66	-11.47	16.65
	cce	216	0.78	75	-2.26	4.38
	fsize	216	16.6	2.19	11.13	19.99
	fage	216	42.95	22.38	2	94
	bsize	216	10.15	2.75	4	18

The variables for this study are abbreviated and are explained as follows: return on assets “roa”, return on equity “roe”, value added intellectual capital “vaic”, human capital efficiency “hce”; structural capital efficiency “sce”; capital employed efficiency “cce”; firm size “fsize”; firms’ age at incorporation “fage”; board size “bsize”

This suggests that there exists a high degree of variation between two financial performance measures from their mean values. This is further reflected in the wide margin between the least and the most performing firms in the industry. Alternatively, intellectual capital indicators do not exhibit a wide margin of variations with their mean values.

Table 2 documents the findings of the pairwise correlation matrix. The result revealed that the degree of correlation of all the variables are within the acceptable rule of thumb of 0.70. The only highly correlated variables are human capital efficiency and value-added intellectual capital with over 90% degree of correlation. This indicated that the two variables are not fit to be modelled together. These two variables are independent and separate indicators for intellectual capital; thus, they are specified differently.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable code	roa	roe	vaic	hce	Sce	cce	Fsize	fage	bsize
Roa	1								
Roe	0.2571*	1							
Vaic	0.3469*	0.2908*	1						
Hce	0.3597*	0.2204*	0.9083*	1					
Sce	0.0327	0.0961	0.4280*	0.0481	1				
Cce	0.0807	0.3585*	0.1927*	-0.0241	0.1389*	1			
Fsize	0.0627	0.2753*	0.2836*	0.2089*	0.132	0.2977	1		
Fage	0.1304	0.2284	-0.0829	-0.1583*	-0.1034	0.3632*	0.4007*	1	
bsize	0.2274*	0.1005	0.022	0.0069	0.0217	0.1317	0.5624*	0.3848*	1

The variables for this study are abbreviated and are explained as follows: return on assets “roa”, return on equity “roe”, value added intellectual capital “vaic”, human capital efficiency “hce”; structural capital efficiency “sce”; capital employed efficiency “cce”; firm size “fsize”; firms’ age at incorporation “fage”; board size “bsize”.

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

This section presents the discussion of findings of the outcome on the relationship between intellectual capital and firm performance based on the panel-spatial correlation coefficients and the random-effect regression estimators. Table 3 presents the analysis in two-folds using the return on assets and return on equity as financial performance indicators, respectively. In the overall, the findings suggest that about 75% of the total variability of financial performance is explained by the model.

Table3: The effect of Intellectual capital on firm performance – PSCC Estimates

Variables	Returns on Assets (ROA)				Returns on Equity (ROE)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
fsize	-0.221*** (-6.52)	-0.225*** (-7.34)	0.2037*** (-4.97)	-232*** (-9.04)	-0.023 (-1.33)	-0.031 (-1.74)	0.015 (1.46)	-0.033 (-1.38)
fage	-0.046 (-1.42)	-0.089** (-2.60)	0.117** (-2.77)	0.072** (-2.08)	0.041** (-2.04)	-0.082*** (-3.36)	-0.152*** (-3.10)	-0.060*** (-2.93)

bsize	0.025** (2.63)	0.018* (1.99)	0.006** (2.10)	0.025** (2.72)	0.015 (1.26)	0.011 (0.85)	0.007 (0.96)	0.017 (1.43)
hce	0.024*** (3.45)	-	-	-	0.019*** (3.29)	-	-	-
sce	-	0.009 (1.07)	-	-	-	0.016** (2.72)	-	-
cce	-	-	0.129*** (6.39)	-	-	-	0.303*** (6.98)	-
vaic	-	-	-	0.021*** (4.67)	-	-	-	0.020*** (5.00)
constant	8.076** (2.29)	12.469*** (3.37)	14.567*** (3.21)	10.761*** (2.95)	4.3986** (2.14)	8.570*** (4.07)	14.067*** (3.06)	6.358*** (3.16)
Year Dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
No. of Obs.	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216
R-Squared	0.7461	0.6835	0.7002	0.7491	0.7602	0.7371	0.8116	0.7759
F-Statistic	41488.15***	4749.23***	1657.44***	9643.15***	17541.43***	2771.05***	113.39***	4839.49***

The variables for this study are abbreviated and are explained as follows: return on assets “roa”, return on equity “roe”, value added intellectual capital “vaic”, human capital efficiency “hce”; structural capital efficiency “sce”; capital employed efficiency “cce”; firm size “fsize”; firms’ age at incorporation “fage”; board size “bsize”. The significance level of the coefficients is denoted as ***, **, * to represent 1%. 5% and 10% respectively while its t-statistics is in parenthesis.

Source: STATA Output, 2021

Starting from individual components of intellectual capital, the findings indicated human capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency has positive and significant impact on performance as measured by the firms' asset and equity returns. For instance, Column [1] & [5] of Table 3 shows that a 1% increase in human capital efficiency implies a 2.4% increase in asset returns and a 1.9% increase in returns on assets, respectively. The findings of this study align with the position of Anifowose, et al. (2018) who documented a positive link between human capital efficiency and firm performance. Subsequently, Column [3] & [5] illustrates that a one-point increase in capital employed efficiency contributes an additional 12.9% and 30.3% to returns on assets and equity respectively. This position contracts the findings of Mohd-Ariff, et al. (2016) who found a non-significant link between capital employed efficiency and financial performance. Structural capital efficiency however, behaves differently in contributing to firms' performance as exposed in the model. Column [2] documents a non-significant impact of structural capital on returns on assets while Column [6] noted a positive and significant impact on returns on equity.

On the overall, value-added intellectual capital significantly improves the performances of firms in the Nigerian consumer goods industry. For instance, Column 4 in Table 3 reveals that a point increase in value-added intellectual capital has an increasing effect of about 2% on the return on assets. Similarly, Column 8 in Table 3 also reveals that an additional point increase in value-added intellectual capital efficiency has about 2.1% on the returns on equity accrued to the firms in the consumer goods industry. The findings on the potency of value-added intellectual

capital conforms with the works of Sardo & Serrasqueiro (2018), who noted that intellectual capital efficiency promotes growth opportunities and financial performances of firms in Europe. On the effects of the confounding variables on the financial performance of firms in the consumer goods industry, it appears that the control variables behave differently on the two measures of financial performance. For instance, the size effect of the firm is found to be negative across all models but only significantly impacts the returns on assets. The reason may be adduced to the fact that size as proxy by the total assets impedes the financial performance of firms in the industry. This finding contradicts the opinion of Tarus, and Sitienei (2015) who found that size significantly improves the firm performance.

Similarly, the firm's age exerts a significant deteriorating influence on the two performance indicators across all the models. The findings suggest that a point increase in the firms' age has an average reductive effect of about 4-8 percent in the returns on assets and equity of the firms. Finally, only the board size has a positive impact on firm financial performance across all models. However, the impact was only significant for the returns on assets. Also, Table 4 presents the summary of the random-effect regression estimates. The findings support the earlier positions documented when the PSCC estimator was employed. The estimates suggest that value-added intellectual capital has a strong and positive influence on financial performance.

Table 4: The effect of Intellectual capital on firm performance: Random Effect Estimates

Variables	Returns on Assets (ROA)				Returns on Equity (ROE)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
fsize	-0.061*** (-3.05)	-0.042** (-1.94)	-0.016 (-0.84)	-0.064*** (-3.20)	-0.582** (-2.36)	-0.051** (-1.98)	0.003 (1.17)	-0.064*** (-2.68)
fage	0.003 (1.37)	0.002** (0.70)	-0.002 (-1.11)	0.001 (1.41)	-0.001 (-0.17)	-0.001 (-0.30)	-0.003 (1.30)	-0.001 (-0.04)
bsize	0.027** (2.48)	0.023* (1.95)	0.021* (1.88)	0.283*** (2.62)	0.013 (1.17)	0.012 (0.95)	0.007 (0.69)	0.015 (1.37)
hce	0.026*** (5.89)	-	-	-	0.020*** (4.29)	-	-	-
sce	-	0.008 (0.90)	-	-	-	0.009* (1.77)	-	-
cce	-	-	0.198*** (4.72)	-	-	-	0.349*** (9.32)	-
vaic	-	-	-	0.023*** (6.01)	-	-	-	0.021*** (5.43)
constant	0.598** (2.00)	0.483* (1.47)	0.029 (0.10)	0.608** (2.05)	1.0088** (2.71)	0.991** (2.587)	0.108 (0.38)	1.039*** (2.89)
Year Dummies	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
No. of Obs.	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216
Wald Statistics	42.46***	6.74	27.68***	43.83***	24.81***	8.14***	90.01***	36.17***

The variables for this study are abbreviated and are explained as follows: return on assets “roa”, return on equity “roe”, value added intellectual capital “vaic”, human capital efficiency “hce”; structural capital efficiency “sce”; capital employed efficiency “cce”; firm size “fsize”; firms’ age at incorporation “fage”; board size “bsize”. The significance level of the coefficients is denoted as ***, **, * to represent 1%, 5% and 10% respectively while its t-statistics is in parenthesis.

The findings indicated that human capital efficiency and capital employed are also crucial capital stocks that could increase the value-addition, competitiveness, and profitability of firms in the consumer goods industry. However, structural capital efficiency maintained a positive but dualistic significance behavior in the model. Structural capital efficiency poses non-significant influence on the returns on assets, whereas it became significant when the return on equity was employed as the dependent variable. The only difference in this result and the latter is the reduction in the significance level from 5% significance level in the latter results to 10% level of significance in the former. That said, the controlling variables exert a similar influence on firm performance as compared to the previous estimates. The size of the firms portrays a significantly declining influence on the two performance measures across the models. On the other hand, the size of board members is positive but significantly influencing the returns on assets.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the impact of intellectual capital on firms' financial performance in the Nigerian consumer goods industry over the period 2008 and 2019. Stemming on the human capital theory and resource-dependency theory, this study links intellectual capital to firm performance indicators using the Driscoll-Kraay panel regression and the random-effect regression models. Further, this study decomposes the value-added intellectual capital into its subcomponents to adequately explore the individual and collective effects of intellectual capital on firm performance. Therefore, the main findings of the study are summarized as thus. First, intellectual capital has a strong and positive contributory effect on firm performance. This implies that intellectual capital improves the efficiency, value addition, and profitability of firms in the consumer goods industry. Second, all the subcomponents of intellectual capital viz; human capital, structural capital, and capital employed exercises positive influences on firm performance. Of all the indicators, human capital efficiency appears to be the most crucial intellectual capital component that drives firm performance, while structural capital exerts a weak influence on firm performance. Furthermore, the findings lay particular credence to board size as a crucial factor for improved firm performance, whereas firm size and age are detrimental to it.

The empirical findings offer some salient policy implications regarding the performance of firms in the consumer goods industry. First, key stakeholders should pay particular attention to the efficient utilization of tangible and intangible assets in the organizations. For instance, policy measures should be embarked upon on the routine disclosure of the performance of intellectual capital assets of the organization. More so, this study exposes the need to identify the

subcomponent of intellectual capital that drives the overall efficiency of value-added intellectual capital in the industry. Second, structural capital efficiency exerts a positive but weak impact on performance. The weak impact may be attributed to the inadequate investments on the structural and organizational capabilities of the firm. Hence, it is expedient on the principal managers to strategically make increased investible decisions on intellectual property rights, patents, and database management to retain operational and trade secrets within the organizations. Finally, the industry's key stakeholders should torchlight extensively on the board composition and size because it critically has positive influence on financial performance. In the overall, the study offers novel empirical insights on the importance of IC to firms in the service and non-service industries. The study affirms that intellectual capital is a strategic resource that drives a firm's competitiveness, growth and sustainability irrespective of whether the firms are knowledge-driven or traditional driven. It offers a salient standpoint for the drivers of the firms in the industry to invest in their intangible capital. This enables them to reap the rare, imitable and nontransferable benefits that accrue to its development and management of intellectual capital. The study further exposes the policymakers to the need to strengthen policy measures on the disclosure of investments on intellectual capital because it will enhance its sound management hence serving as a key criterion for attracting investments into the industry. This is because the public availability of information on intellectual capital development will deepen investors' knowledge on potential investment decisions.

Although this study reveals appealing outcomes of the impact of intellectual capital on firm performance in the consumer good industry, however, its applicability to other non-service firms and industries may not be guaranteed. This may be due to the industry-specific factors that may influence the relationship. Hence, interested scholars in the intellectual capital field may seek to extend the study to other non-service sectors so as to make a robust comparison of the analysis. Equally, the scope of the study may be extended to other consumer goods industries in other developing countries, particularly Africa. The mediating effect of institutional development may also be considered. Finally, the relationship between the variables may be subjected to other estimation methods for further comparative analysis of the findings

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